

Munir's Model of Teacher Identity Exploration

Note: This model has gained recognition from educators in more than 75 countries.

In recent times, teaching has been equated to an act of slavery. The principal motivation of teachers is to establish a bubble rapport and create a calibrated identity for survival- not in all, but in most cases. The emergent norm in this profession is to pacify others and seek affiliation, leading to delusional and draining expectations. In this context, teaching has been reduced to the art of puppetry. Munir's Model of Teachers' Identity Exploration aids in understanding the ethical aspects of leadership.

Adjustment of identity in diverse context

Continuous personal and professional development

Identity is a continuous multi-layered crypto-cyclic process of building a true relationship, with oneself followed by others. There is an intersectionality between identities, but we often weigh others' identities, in particular, familial and relational, over personal, which sometimes, is risky to personal well-being.

Identity is an interplay of ideas and realities, brought to the forefront through the complex dynamics of self-exposure, self-interaction, and the reciprocal engagement between the self and others.

There is a blurred boundary between personal and professional identity. However, it is important to establish clarity in this distinction. Teachers should consciously revisit and reflect on their identity as the initial reference point for developing a professional identity. This dynamic process is not restricted by age, experience, or time limitations.

This model has two dimensions: the personal dimension and the professional dimension.

The process of teacher professional identity begins with self-identity exploration- the most convoluted yet rewarding process. The teacher needs to discover who they are, i.e., identify gender, cultural, spiritual, social, relational, familial, national, moral, and associated identities, while suspending their biases momentarily. They should unveil, which of these identities are drawing

positive and challenging impacts on their well-being. For this purpose, ethrical reflection, resilience, intellectual openness, and exposure to realities are crucial. During this longitudinal process, they should not delve deeply into the reasons behind actual realities but rather gather a pool of information about self from at least quadripartite domains.

Next, recognize and filter personal values, goals, and boundaries, and identify a fabricated set of values.

A teacher then dives into reflective practices to identify personal strengths and areas for improvement. This process can be challenging since personal strengths are often influenced by social constructs, while areas of improvement may be overlooked. Therefore, this cyclical phase must be reiterated to exclude external influences.

A teacher must also recognize personal insecurities such as those related to relationships, and delve into identifying the causes without seeking affiliation. Munir believes that teachers tend to keep insecurities in their subconsciousness, which could be detrimental to self-acceptance and could later affect their teaching.

The teacher must then cultivate self-acceptance. Before making any decisions, they should prioritize their thoughts and needs. While this may resonate with egoism in some ways, this model, represents a serene phase of reflection and self-acceptance.

In the next phase, teachers consistently identify toxic relationships and remove insincere people from their lives. With time, they learn the art of filtering for affiliation which has offered them temporal satisfaction in the past. Although this task may present challenges and appear unrealistic, over time, they can navigate their path more smoothly.

In the subsequent phase of Munir's Model of Teacher Identity Exploration, teachers reflect on the purpose of their lives and consider the things that could bring them happiness. This reflection serves as a foundation for identifying their professional identity.

Professional identity is a combination of several elements, for example, competence, recognition, motivation, experience and exposure, belongingness, values, commitment, ethical leadership, emotions, care, participation, and professional networking. Munir asserts that our tendency to prioritize experience above all can result in intellectual vanity. Experience alone does not guarantee someone's proficiency. Instead, it is the breadth and depth of exposure within those experiences that hold greater significance and should be given more weightage.

To explore professional identity, the teacher needs to gain a deeper understanding of the nature of the job, including roles and responsibilities, tasks, commitment, working relationships, and opportunities for professional development. Based on this understanding, the teacher must decide if teaching aligns with their personal and professional identity. This decision determines the teacher's level of commitment, motivation, and job satisfaction in the long run.

Next, the teacher should engage in a process of skill reassessment, identifying areas for improvement that are specific to their role as an educator. It's crucial to acknowledge and address any deficiencies in their skills. For instance, if a teacher lacks digital literacy, they should seek assistance to improve their skills via networking. Conversely, if they excel in certain areas, such

as action research or writing reflective diaries, they should share expertise with colleagues. Munir underlines, “Vulnerability is the beauty of teaching. Revealing a certain level of vulnerability can cultivate resilience, and foster a mindset of continuous reflection and learning. However, showcasing all of your skills and talents extensively may lead to arrogance or make others feel inferior, potentially resulting in the misuse of your intellectual abilities or limiting the opportunities for intellectual growth.”

In the words of Munir, "You will find snakes, crocodiles, mosquitoes, scorpions, hippos, and bugs in your surroundings. They will never appreciate your competence unless you build fake rapport and benefit them. They might create a hindrance to your professional growth if you expose realities. Be honest! Sometimes, it is good to remain silent, while at others, be vocal. Revenge should be avoided. Respect yourself and others in their professional interactions. Being flexible and adaptable is essential, but it should be done with dignity and endurance."

The teacher then needs to adjust their approach to teaching in a diverse educational context. This phase does not require teachers to compromise their values or beliefs, but rather to accommodate a multicultural environment. Teachers can share their ideologies but recommend not sharing sensitive ideologies with learners.

Finally, the teacher is expected to continue putting efforts into improving personal and professional well-being.

Overall, teachers should avoid neglecting their personal lives and make time for themselves, their families, and their hobbies. By doing so, they can value their mental health and become better teachers. Moreover, the model emphasizes the importance of communication and networking. Teachers should communicate with their colleagues, participate in online communities, and collaborate with people from different backgrounds (from known to unknown). They should establish ethical relationships with their students, parents, and other stakeholders in the education sector.

According to Dr. Munir, teaching is not a profession but rather a reflective journey that leads to optimism, improvement, selfless devotion, and life-long learning. Teachers are the symbol of altruism. Genuine teachers don't contest for popularity or seek counterfeit affiliation. Their prime concern is not to pull someone's leg, but rather explore teaching identity, and help themselves and others grow ethically and intellectually.

Dr. Munir recommends, “Global policymakers should introduce the following courses in teacher education degree programs to promote the re-creation of knowledge, accelerate learning independencies and support innovative teaching practices, rather than solely relying on on-going professional development workshops and training sessions: Educational Neuroscience, Heutagogy in Education, Inclusive Language, Future Studies in Education, Artificial Intelligence in Education, Block Chaining in Education, Digital Literacy, Gamification, Edupreneurship, Environmental Literacy, Mental Health Literacy, Global Citizenship Education, Human Rights Education, Basic Research Literacy, Early Childhood Literacy, School Literacy, Adult Literacy, and Elderly Literacy.”